

**CRITICAL REVIEW ON PARIKARTIKA AND ITS MANAGEMENT W.S.R.T FISSURE
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ABSTRACT

Anal fissure is very painful anorectal disease. Health of an individual depends upon his diet environmental condition and lifestyle in the present era of fast food, due to busy schedule, there is put irregularity in the dietary habits and people are adopting sedentary lifestyle. Due to which there is disturbance in the digestive system which results in many diseases. Anorectal diseases like fissure in ano, haemorrhoid, fistula in ano etc. could also be considered as a problem originated from disturbed digestive system due to bad food habits and improper lifestyle. In Ayurveda it can be correlated to Parikartika. Parikartika is not mentioned as a separate disease entity in Ayurvedic text. It is described as complication of Bastikarma Vyapad^[1], Vamana- virechana Vyapad^[2] and as Garbjini Vyapad.^[3] It is also explained as the Arsh Purva Roopa, Updrava of Atisara and Vyapad of Grabhini. The first reference of the disease Parikartika is presented by Sushruta Samhita. It has symptoms like pain, burning sensation, bleeding per rectum, constipation etc.

KEYWORDS: basti, Kartanwat, Vaman, Virechana, Parikartika, Fissure in ano.**INTRODUCTION**

Parikartika is the most common cause of pain in anal region. It is commonly found in pregnant women, purporeal period and youngsters Nowadays. It is most painful condition affecting the anal region. About 30 to 40% of the population suffer from anal problems and anal fissure comprises of 10 to 15% of anorectal disorder and is characterized by excruciating pain during and after defecation and bleeding along with stool with spasm of anal sphincter. Our lifestyle is change, so as nature, which has great reflection in our health. Parikartika means Parikartanavat Vedana around Gudapradesh. It means cutting type of pain, but the sentinel tag like features are not in the reference of Parikartika. Sentinel tag can be compare with Shushkarsh as mentioned by Charak Samhita. It is mention as sign and symptom of other diseases or complication of Ayurvedic procedure or due to the some instrumentaion, like enema nozzle.

MATERIAL AND METHOD**Definition**

According to Acharya Sushruta, Parikartika is a situation in which there is cutting pain in Guda, Nabhi and

surrounding areas. An anal fissure (synonym, fissure-in ano) is a longitudinal split in the anoderm of the distal anal canal which extends from the anal verge proximally towards, but not beyond, the dentate line.^[4]

Nirukti- Parikartika word is derived from the Sanskrit word "Pari" which means "all around" and "Kartanam"^[5] means "the act of cutting".^[6] So in Parikartika there is excessive cutting pain around the anus. According to Dalhana, there is cutting and tearing pain everywhere around the anus.

Synonyms: The synonyms for Parikartika are Ksata Guda and Ksata Payu.

Nidana: Acharya Sushrut and Acharya Charaka described about Nidana, Samprapti, Lakshana, and Chikitsa of Parkartika at different places. The precipitating and predisposing factors of any disease are commonly called its Nidana. The etiological factors of Parikartika can be divided in three types as per Acharya Sushruta.

- 1. Nija Hetu (Endogenous factors):** Nija Hetu means Dosha Prakopak Hetu. Hence, all factors responsible for vitiation of Vata Dosha^[7] can be considered under Nija Hetu of Parikartika because Vedana (pain) is the chief symptom of Parikartika and also Guda is the main site for Vata Dosha especially Apana Vayu. Some factors responsible for vitiation of Vata Dosha mentioned in classics, are Tikta, Lavana and Kasaya food, Ruksha and Alpa Anna Sevana. Pitta vitiated factors like Katu, Amla, Lavana Ahara, Krodha, diurnal etc are also responsible for disease.
 - If Vamana and Virechana with Teekshna, Ushna and Pitta Prakopaka medicine is given to the patients having Mridu Koshta and Mandaagni then Pitta and Vata Prakopa leads to Parikartika.^[9]
 - The Rough introduction of Basti Netra also causes ulcer in anus and related pain^[10]
 - Basti Netra which is big in size and having rough surface also causes ulcer in anus^[11]
 - If Basti of Ati Tikshna, Ushna and Lavana Dravya given to patient^[12]
 - Atiyoga of Virechana^[13]
 - Charaka has also mentioned Parikartika as complication of Vamana and Virechana^[14]
 - Sharangadhara has also mentioned 76 complications of Basti and Parikartika is one among them.
 - In Charakasamhita, Sushruthasamhita and in Astanga Sangraha Parikartika is mentioned as one among the Lakshanas of Basti Karma Vyapat.^[15-17]
- 2. Aagantuja Hetu (Exogenous factors):** The trauma at Guda leads to Parikartika. During the procedure of Basti or Virechana, complications may develop in the form of Parikartika. It may happen due to rough and thick Basti Netra.^[8]
- 3. Nidanarthakari Roga (Complications of other diseases)-**Like due to faulty procedure-

The specific etiology related to the disease and physician

Related to the disease	Related to Physician
Udavarta, Purisajaudavarta or purisavrtavata- The initiating factor in the development of a fissure is trauma to the anal canal, usually in the form of the passage of a fecal bolus that is large and hard.	Virechana Vyapada- A person having Mrdukostha and with Alpabala if ingests Tikshna, Usna and Ruksha drugs for Virechana, then this disease result.
Arsa (Prodromal features, and symptoms of vatika and kaphajaarsa, Abnormality of the internal sphincter predisposes the patient to the formation of both haemorrhoid and fissure.	Basti Vyapada (niruha)- If Ruksha Basti containing Tikshna and Lavana drugs is administered in heavy dose; it may produce Parikartika.
Jirnajwara- Generalized dehydration of the body, so the bowels are not clear, causing the disease	Excessive use of Yapana Basti- It may lead to Parikartika along with other diseases.
Atisara- (Vatikaatisara, After an attack of diarrhea the sphincters loose their capacity to dilate and go into severe spasm.	Basti Netra Vyapada- Due to inappropriate administration of enema nozzle and defect in enema nozzle itself may cause this disease.
Vatikagrahan- Ulcerative colitis, Crohn's disease the Anal fissure also very common.	

Samprapti

Aacharya Sushruta has described the pathogenesis of each disease in the form of Shatkriya Kala^[18], These are Sanchaya, Prakopa, Prasara, Sthana Sanshraya, Vyakti and Bheda. In Parikartika the main vitiated Dosha is Vata. Dushya are Twak, Rakta, Mansa

Lakshana of parikartika

The patient suffers from cutting pain with burning sensation in anus, umbilicus, penis and neck of bladder, retention of flatus and anorexia.^[19]

Acharya Charaka has mentioned the symptom i.e. severe pain in anus while describing.

Parikartika as a complication of Vamana and Virechana. Aacharya Sushruta, in chapter of Vamana, Virechana Vyaapada has mentioned the cardinal symptom of Parikartika that is sharp cutting and burning pain in Guda. In Parikartika, Dushta Vrana in Guda is one

symptom in the form of longitudinal shaped ulcer in anal region. The description of symptoms of Parikartika mentioned in Sushruta Samhita is absolutely correct because clinical symptoms of fissure in latest text of surgery are same.

Types

Acharya Kashyapa described about 3 types of Parikartika in the Garbhini Chikitsa according to Dosha:-Vatika, Patika, Kaphaja.

Sadhyasadhya

The Vrana which occurs in Guda Pradesh can be easily cured (Su.Su.23/5).

When Parikartika is in its Vyakt Avastha then it is Sukhasadhya because it affects the superficial layer of Guda Pradesh. But when it affects the deeper layer of Guda Pradesh in

Bhedaavastha, it becomes Krichchhasadhya which need Sastra Karma. When we consider Parikartika as Varna then it can be easily treated if patient have good Satva, Mamsa Dhatu, Agni, and in younger stage. If it is left untreated then it becomes Yapya and finally to Asadhyatwa stage.

Treatment

1. To check the vitiated Vata and Pitta.
2. To combat the abdominal disorder because Vata and Pitta are mostly vitiated which leads to many complication.

Diet^[20]

- Madhura and Brihaniya diet, advised in thin & lean patient.
- Langhana-Deepana and Ruksha - Ushna - Laghu diet. advised in Sama condition.
- Devdaaru and Tila Kalka with Ushnodaka
- In severe Vata Prakopa Avastha, Ghrit with Daadima Rasa should be given.
- Ashvattha, Udumbaar, Plaksha and Kadamba Siddha milk.

Local Treatment

Different type of Basti Karmas are described for local management.

Patient should be treated with Karbudaradi Basti mixed with paste or decoction of Karbudar, Aadhki, Kadambchaal and Vetas Siddha with Ksheer along with Madhu and Sharkara. Gambhaar and Kachanaar Vrint's paste mix with milk, honey, Sharkara and give Sheetvasti. Most of the drugs, which are used in Basti Karma are Vata Shamak, Vrana Ropak and Pitta Shamak.

Surgical procedures

In chronic fissure-Lord's dilatation, posterior sphincterotomy, lateral anal sphincterotomy, excision of anal ulcer, anal advancement flap.

DISCUSSION

The disease parikartika occur due to pitta and vata. Due to these etiological factors vitiated doshas get accumulated in the guda region. The disease is most common in middle age group. Vata and pitta doshas are mainly involved in Parikartika. Passage of hard stool is main cause of tear in lower part of anal canal. Charaka mention that if a drastic purgative drug is taken by one having snigdha guru koshta and aama dosha or by other having mridu koshta, alpa bala it expel impurity along with aama, shortly on reaching the anal region and then causes severe colic, cutting pain and slimy discharge with blood. So, before prescribing medicine for Sanshodhana or to treat constipated patient, care of Saama Nirama condition of koshta and roughness of body is very important, otherwise medicine may cause Parikartika. In the treatment of Parikartika, if the patient having aama, then langhan pachana ruksha is indicated, i.e. hot and light food should bde prescribed, and if the patient is weak and his body is ruksha then sweet and bringhaniya food should be recommended.

CONCLUSION

Parikartika is very common among ano rectal diseases which occur due to improper Aahar- Vihar. Most of the acute cases get cured by Ayurvedic management, whereas modern treatment does not gives response in more than 50% cases. Therefore, before prescribing the drastic purgatives for Sanshodhan Chikitsa or during the treatment of Parikartika, the condition of Sama-Nirama, body constitutions, Kostha and secondary causes of Parikartika should be examined properly. In Parikartika there is cutting type of pain in anal region which resembles the symptom of Fissure-in-ano. That's why Parikartika is correlated with Fissure-in-ano in modern science. Initially where the disease is still not occur we can thought it involve only rasa dhatu i.e. disease will manifest if apathya sevan is going on which is nothing but acute fissure. In acute fissure there is severe pain and bleeding and angry ulcer is also visible. As the disease progress the fissure in ano when become chronic as per body own compensatory mechanism there is formation of anal polyp above the ulcer and below there is sentinel tag. The general principal of treatment is removing the cause and treats the disease. The agni should be maintain as well as the proper environment should be provided for proper healing. The conventional treatment is sufficient rarely needs surgical intervention. A Guda parikartika is a disease itself, where it is undergone various stages and also there is involvement of Dosas, when it is associated with other disease it also follow the same rule.

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